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JOB PROPITIATION AND GLADNESS AMONG INDIAN RAILWAY EMPLOYEES WITH REFERENCE TO SOUTH CENTRAL RAILWAY (SCR).

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ABSTRACT

The total of all the elements that significantly influence a person's capacity and actual output to carry out any particular type of job is characterized as their degree of Job Propitiation and Gladness. Both externally (non-controllable) and internally (controllable) the workplace, job propitiation and joy components start and evolve. The sum of all physiological, psychological, and environmental aspects that either make a person content or unsatisfied with their career is known as job satisfaction and joy. Evaluations, thoughts, deeds, and behaviors are some of the outcomes of job satisfaction and happiness. Job satisfaction and joy increase productivity because happy employees are more likely to put in extra time and effort. On the other hand, staff members who dislike their jobs could Additionally, there is a potential of increased absenteeism and personnel turnover. The more dedicated the workers are to their task, the more will be produced as a consequence of their efforts. The purpose of this study is to examine the many elements that influence job satisfaction and job promotion among personnel of the Vijayawada Division of the South Central Railway Division of the Indian Railways, as well as the challenges they face and potential solutions. An important division of Indian Railways is the Vijayawada Division.

Keywords: *Job Propitiation, Gladness, Railway employee's satisfaction.*

INTRODUCTION

An individual's collection of good and/or negative thoughts about their employment is referred to as their level of employee satisfaction. Life happiness includes a sense of fulfillment at work. It is the level of satisfaction or joy brought on by a work. An emotional reaction to a job is called work satisfaction. One of the most talked-about and extensively studied subjects in organizational psychology is job satisfaction (Spector, 1997). According to Locke (1976), job satisfaction is an enjoyable or pleasant emotional state brought on by an evaluation of one's employment or professional experiences. Job happiness has been investigated as a result of several human and workplace factors as well as an antecedent to numerous results. According to Lease (1998), employees who are more pleased with their jobs are often less absent, less likely to quit, more productive, more likely to show organizational commitment, and more likely to be content with their life. Numerous variables might have an impact on someone's degree of job satisfaction. In addition to pay and benefits, other important factors to consider are the job itself (the variety of tasks required, the interest and challenge the job generates, and the clarity of the job description/requirements), leadership and social relationships, the quality of working conditions, and the promotion system within the company. People are thought to be more content with their jobs the happier they are in their jobs. Since the human relations method has grown so well-liked, the idea of work happiness has become more important. There are several complicated factors, circumstances, emotions, and behavioral patterns that affect job satisfaction.

HOW TO IMPROVE EMPLOYEE SATISFACTION

The morale of the firm is often reflected in employee attitudes. Because they represent the firm to the public, happy workers are crucial in areas like customer service and sales.

1. **Communication that is Clear, Concise, and Consistent:** In many firms, employees are unaware of the purpose, vision, and objectives. Gaining the most from the skills or abilities each employee brings to the company may be accomplished by creating a corporate culture that demands employees to be an important part of the business. Employees should be kept up to date on the firm's status, accomplishments, problems, and how they directly contribute to the success of the organization.
2. **Getting to Know Your Employees and Building a Team:** This is accomplished by selecting the best candidate for the job and by outlining and communicating employee expectations. Every corporation should invest time in fostering a culture of cooperation in order to overcome obstacles, forge new advantages, and help the company achieve greater success. This culture should be based on trust and responsibility.
3. **Improvement Programs and Training:** Give them the required instruction, mentoring, and coaching to improve their abilities and demonstrate your interest in their success and preparation for increased responsibilities.
4. **Give Employees More Power Across the Company:** Increase New Responsibilities to Appropriate Levels Across the Company. Encourage proper decision-making and let those who are most familiar with the situation decide. Make sure the employee is aware of your confidence in their abilities to perform their duties.
5. **The Work Itself:** By implementing work rotation, job enlargement—such as knowledge and task enlargement—and job enrichment, we may raise employee happiness. Employees should have access to the target
6. **Fair Compensation and Benefits:** Compensation and benefit policies are the most crucial components of a corporation. However, you should base your rules on “suitability” rather than “the best”.
7. **Chance for Promotion and Career Development:** Create initiatives to advance all organizational titles, as well as initiatives to advance each title's career. Every person should be given the chance to use their strengths, skills, and creativity in the workplace.
8. **Track Performance and Recognize Contributions:** People are naturally scorekeepers. Take advantage of this by keeping an eye on good conduct and contributions and rewarding appropriately. Encourage people to perform at higher levels by letting them know how they are doing. The right assessment system should be established, and we should encourage people to work hard.
9. **Offer Regular, Honest input:** Don't wait until there is a problem before offering input. Instead, encourage loyalty, set high performance standards, and keep things honest while providing regular, constructive feedback on the employee's performance across a range of difficulties.
10. **Provide the best tools and safe working conditions:** Make an investment in your staff by ensuring that their tools and equipment don't hinder their achievement. Give them the greatest equipment so they can perform at their very best for the business, the clients, and the market. Companies should have a program for workplace health and safety.

REVIEWS ON STUDY

Vaddi.Ramesh, Dr.Ashok Kumar Katta (2023), The Guntakal Railway Division's workers' happiness is a fascinating topic to me. Most of the company's workers are pleased with the results. It's reasonable to conclude that the majority of people are aware of and trust the company's plan. Most workers are rewarded for their hard work. Railroads who pay their employees well will remain in business. Similarly to how members of a family work together to accomplish a shared objective, workers

in a company should do the same. Each and every day people are given the chance to show off their talents and get praise. The highest levels of government are easy to get in touch with.

Vaddi.Ramesh, Dr.Ashok Kumar Katta (2022), It is the whole of all elements that have a huge affect on an individual’s capability to do any given work and their authentic output that contributes to job satisfaction. Job pride factors originate and develop each outdoor (non controllable) and internally (controllable) in the working individual’s surroundings. Employment pride is the whole of all physiological, psychological, and conditional elements that both fulfill or dissatisfy an worker with his or her work. Findings on job pride have implications for evaluating, thinking, behaving, and feeling. The intention of this learn about is to check out various factors of work happiness, difficulties, and corrective strategies impacting railway personnel working in the Guntakal Division of the indian railways’ south central railway division. The Guntakal Division of indian railways is placed on the vijayawada route. Guntakal is the administrative centre for six districts’ railway requirements. Divisional Railway Manager (DRM) in Guntakal is the predominant administrative and regulatory body.

Vaddi.Ramesh, Dr.Ashok Kumar Katta (2022), There are countless elements that make contributions to an individual’s capacity to do any given job and their authentic output. External and interior elements make a contribution to job satisfaction, which might also be influenced by means of the working individual’s environment. True, job pride might also have each superb and horrific results on the individual, the firm, and the nation. In order to decide if an worker is cosy with his or her employment, we appear at a range of physiological, psychological, and environmental elements. Emotional, cognitive, behavioural, and evaluative repercussions of job delight results. For this study, the fundamental goal is to check out how a range of job delight elements and challenges have an effect on railway employees in the Guntakal Railway Division of India’s South Central Railway.

Ashok Kumar and Bala Nageswara Rao, (2015) The assertion claims that Indian railroads are the most expensive in terms of human resources and expenditures associated with staff (workers on rolls plus pension). Employees account for more than 61% of total operating expenditures.

IMPLICATIONS

Objective: to determine what factors affect employees in the commercial and transport departments in terms of job Propitiation and Gladness.

METHODOLOGY

The present study have a sample of 167 Respondents of employees and used multistage sampling. Data collected from Vijayawada Railway station. Data reduction uses a factor analysis technique. The current study examines many aspects of employee work satisfaction. Here, the researcher evaluates work satisfaction using three main factors. Organizational considerations come after the first and most significant one. 17 generally used variables, including Recognition, Safety, On-time payment, Salaries, Challenges, Security, Policies, Welfare, Performance, Skills, Transparency, Promotions, Payments, Benefits, Working conditions, Work load, and Autonomy, were taken for the study’s purposes. The complete set of data has been condensed into a smaller set of variables with the use of factor analysis.

Table 1: KMO AND BARTLETT’S TEST		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.572
Bartlett’s Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	231.612
	Df	124
	Sig.	.001

The high Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin score in Table 1 (0.572 >.05) shows how beneficial a factor analysis would be for the available data. Bartlett’s test of sphericity’s significant value is 0.001 and is less than.05, indicating that there are significant correlations between the variables. The KMO and Bartlett tests’ results show that the current data is particularly valuable for factor analysis.

Component	Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative%
1	1.373	8.684	8.684
2	1.532	15.424	24.108
3	1.432	28.368	52.476
4	1.444	38.173	90.649

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis (PCA).

Table 2 provides information on overall variance (including cumulative percentage). Four factors are formed via factor analysis of the variables. 90% of the variation is explained by four components.

S.NO	FACTORS	Components			
		1	2	3	4
1	IR recognizes and rewards employees who show outstanding performance in their work	.654			
2	IR provides welfare facilities to the satisfaction of employees	.581			
3	The wages and salaries paid by IR are as good as being paid by other transport companies	.515			
4	IR pays wages and salaries on time	.498			
5	The working conditions in IR are good	.417			
6	IR gives utmost importance to safety		.688		
7	Promotions are based on the suitability of the promote rather than on favoritism		.639		
8	IR pays bonus and other benefits from time to time		.622		
9	The policies of IR are just and fair			.635	
10	The work load in IR is in manageable Limits			.555	
11	Autonomy exists in IR			.424	
12	Promotions are timely in IR			.413	
13	Employees in IR are given opportunities to use their skills and abilities			.409	
14	IR pays good wages and salaries				.617
15	Indian railways (IR) provides job security				.556
16	The job is challenging in IR				.449
17	The methods adopted to promote employees are Transparency and fair				.423

When the Eigen value of all four components is more than 1, it indicates a variance of 90.649 percent, and the remaining variances are displayed in the table. The first element makes for 8.684% of the total, followed by the second factor (15.424%), the third factor (28.368%), and the final factor (38.173%). Total variance of 90.649 percent identifies the main factors that any employee would take into account when assessing work satisfaction.

The statements are into 4 components of factoranalysis.

The following 5 statements come under single factor. (1-5)

- IR recognizes and rewards employees who show outstanding performance in theirwork
- IR provides welfare facilities to the satisfaction ofemployees
- ThewagesandsalariespaidbyIRareasgoodasbeingpaidbyother transportcompanies
- IR pays wages and salaries ontime
- The working conditions in IR aregood.

The following 3 statements come under single factor. (6-8)

- IR gives utmost importance tosafety
- Promotions are based on the suitability of the promote rather thanon favoritism
- IR pays bonus and other benefits from time totime

The following 5 statements come under single factor. (9-13)

- The policies of IR are just andfair
- The work load in IR is in manageablelimits
- Autonomy exists inIR
- Promotions are timely inIR
- Employees in IR are given opportunities to use their skills andabilities

The following 4 statements come under single factor. (14-17)

- IR pays good wages andsalaries
- Indian railways (IR) provides jobsecurity
- The job is challenging inIR
- The methods adopted to promote employees are Transparency and fair

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Organizational vs. Designation Factors:

Here, the independent sample T test outcome is expected. The variable often has a meaningful value larger than 0.05. It suggests that all individuals who work in IR have a similar perspective on organizational variables.

Organizational vs. Departmental Factors:

The bulk of the variables in the study have significant values more than 5%, which suggests that both personnel in the transport and commercial departments have similar perceptions of organizational issues.

In this regard, the study displays the variance of the remaining variables and 90.649 percent. The first element makes for 8.684% of the total, followed by the second factor (15.424%), the third factor (28368%), and the final factor (38.173%).

CONCLUSION

Based on the foregoing considerations, we may conclude that employee attitudes frequently reflect the corporate culture. Because they represent the firm to the public, happy workers are crucial in areas like customer service and sales. To improve employee performance and productivity, which eventually leads to high profits, satisfied customers, and customer retention, every firm should adopt tactics that improve the work environment, boost staff morale, and promote employee happiness. When it comes to managing their personnel, one of the most challenging issues modern managers face is job satisfaction. In order to satisfy their employees, policy makers and management have focused on offering a variety of amenities to their workforce. A positive work atmosphere and conducive working circumstances may boost employee job satisfaction and encourage them to provide their best efforts, which will improve their work performance.

REFERENCES

1. Ashok Kumar and Bala Nageswara Rao (2015), Performance of Indian railways towards employees job satisfaction with reference to Vijayawada division, International Journal of Current Research, February, Vol.7, Issue.02, pp.12980-12982.
2. Vaddi. Ramesh, Ashok Kumar Katta (2023). Indian railway employees' job satisfaction at the Guntakal division. International Journal of Health Sciences, 6(S1), 1151-1158.
3. Vaddi.Ramesh, Dr.Ashok Kumar Katta (2022), A Study of Employee Job Satisfaction with Special Reference to the South Central Railway's Guntakal Division, International Journal of Mechanical Engineering, Vol. 7 No. 2, ISSN: 0974-5823.Pp-3478-3483.
4. Vaddi.Ramesh, Dr.Ashok Kumar Katta (2022), Indian Railways Employees Job Satisfaction: A Prospective Case Study on Guntakal Division South Central Railway Zone, International Journal of Mechanical Engineering, Vol. 7 No. 2, ISSN: 0974-5823.Pp-3484—3488.
5. <http://www.indianrail.gov.in>
6. <http://www.indianrailways.gov.in>
7. <http://www.irwo.in>
8. <http://www.planningcommission.nic.in>
9. <http://www.scr.indianrailways.gov.in>
10. Annual Reports and Accounts of Indian Railways, Government of India (Ministry of Railways).
11. Booklet, Master Circular and Staff Benefit Fund - Letter/ Note/ Manual by South Eastern Railway Board.
12. Indian Rail Worker published by the Employees Union of Indian Railway (EUIR)
13. Indian Railways Establishment Rule/ Manual
14. Indian Railways Year Book.